

BIODIESEL PRODUCTION FROM *Ziziphus abyssinica* HOCHST. EX A. RICH. (RHAMNACEAE) SEED OIL USING MODIFIED MAGNETIC SAND AS HETEROGENEOUS CATALYST

Bukar Wakil^{1*}, Onen Alfred², Aisha Bukar Zanna³, Joseph Clement Akan⁴, James Yakubu⁴, Mohammed Goni⁵, Umar Tanko Mamza⁴

¹Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Federal University Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

²Department of Chemical Sciences, Faculty of Pure and Applied Sciences, Federal University, Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria.

³Department of Chemistry, Borno State University, Nigeria

⁴Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

⁵Department of Remedial and General Studies, Mohammed Goni College of Legal and Islamic Studies, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author's Email Address: bukarwakil87@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Biodiesel is an alternative fuel made from renewable biological sources such as vegetable oils (both edible and non-edible oil) and animal fats. This study aimed to produce biodiesel from Zizipus abyssinica using magnetic sand as heterogeneous catalyst. The catalyst was characterized using both physical and X-ray diffraction, (XRD) techniques. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyzed the crystal structure and particle size in order to obtain information on the surface area of catalyst. Physicochemical analysis of Zizipus abyssinica seed oil revealed that ash content was 0.04 %, specific gravity (0.98), moisture content (0.07 %), acid value (4.38 %), free fatty acid (2.19 %), viscosity (4.93 cSt) and pH 6.8. The energy dispersive X-ray of magnetic sand revealed that silicon and potassium have the higher atomic and weight concentration while iron and titanium show no concentration as presented. The characterization results revealed high atomic concentration of Si (77.14 %), followed by K (10.92 %), Al (4.77 %), Ca (1.50%), Fe (1.36 %), S (1.11%), Ag (0.66 %), Mg (0.60 %), Zr (0.60 %) and Na (0.27 %). The main peaks of 19.40, 21.50 250 270, 280, 28.80, 370. 400, 40.70, 50.70, 55.30, 60.30, 650 and 690 were all present in the XRD spectrum of Sand/MgO, intensities have significantly increased. The size of the crystal was measured to be 100 μm with uniform distribution. The variation of amount of catalyst [W%] was methyl ester yield, the most notable catalyst used in producing biodiesel is the homogeneous alkaline catalyst which is due to their higher kinetic reaction rates. The magnetic sand was found to exhibit catalytic activity in the conversion of Ziziphus abyssinica seed oil to its methyl-ester as further proved by FT – IR analysis. A discovery such as this is indeed an addition to the indigenous catalyst that are cheaper and easily accessible.

Keywords: *Ziziphus abyssinica*; Biodiesel; Catalyst; X-ray Diffraction (XRD); Seed Oil

INTRODUCTION

Biodiesel is an alternative fuel made from renewable biological sources such as vegetable oils (both edible and non-edible oil) and animal fats. Vegetable oils are usually esters of glycol with different chain length and degree of saturation [1]. Biodiesel, a promising substitute as an alternative fuel has gained significant attention due to the predicted scarcity of conventional fuels and environmental concerns [1]. This is a viable solution that can generate profits for small scale farmers and also create better life quality for rural workforce [2]. With the increase in petroleum price and the environmental concerns about pollution, Biofuel's potentials have expanded because of many advantages such as its environmental friendliness and its better efficiency than fossil fuel [3]. Many countries throughout the world are trying hard to expand the utilization field of biodiesel in their industrial development [3]. Currently, more than 95% commercial productions of biodiesel are from edible oils such as soybean oil, rape seed oil and palm oil, which can be obtained on a large scale from the agro-based industry [4].

Fossil fuels are also considered as the main source of local environmental pollution. Thus, alternative energy sources based on sustainable, renewable and environmentally friendly processes are urgently needed. One of the most prominent alternative energy resources, attracting more and more interest in recent years with the price for crude oil reaching record heights, is biodiesel, which is a possible substitute for petroleum-based diesel fuel. Many studies have shown that the properties of biodiesel are very close to diesel fuel [5].

Biodiesel is produced through esterification and transesterification reactions of vegetable oil and animal fats with an alcohol; methanol or ethanol is usually the alcohol for biodiesel preparation. The reaction is facilitated with a suitable catalyst either homogeneous or heterogeneous. Today, biodiesel compared with petroleum is considered an environmentally friendly fuel due to low carbon dioxide emissions, biodegradable fuel, high cetane number, high combustion efficiency, lower aromatic, and sulphur content in comparison to petroleum diesel. These makes biodiesel a competitive fuel in the market [6].

Biodiesel production aims to get good qualities and quantities by choosing suitable and cheap feedstock such as virgin vegetable oils, spent cooking oils and animals' fats. In this study, *Ziziphus abyssinica* oil was used for biodiesel production. Other types of edible vegetable oil can be used, for instance; soybean oil, sunflower, palm oil, canola and peanut oil or even non-edible oils such as sea mango, jatropha, rubber seed and pongamia pinnata [4]. In the present work, the most matured and widely-used method in biodiesel production is adopted i.e. using a heterogeneous catalyst [7]. Four instrumental analyses were carried out to analyze the catalyst, the biodiesel products, and seed oils in detail. X-ray diffraction (XRD), which is used to analyze crystal structure and particle size in order to obtain information on the surface area of the catalyst, X-ray fluorescence is used to determine the chemical composition of magnetic sand, viscometer was used to determined viscosity, and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), was used to characterize the *Ziziphus abyssinica* methyl-ester.

Ziziphus abyssinica [Fig. 1], commonly called Catch thorn and "Magarya" in Hausa language is a spiny shrub or tree that grows up to 4m high in the Sahel and drier part of tropical Africa. The *Z. abyssinica* is a tree/shrub or climber of 1.8-8m. Its bark is grey, deeply furrowed and branches are almost zigzag, with single or paired thorns of up to 12 mm. It is found in wooded grassland, bushed grassland and along rivers. Its cream pulp and outer skin are edible. The pulp has a sweet to slightly bitter taste but edible portion is small. It is also used for construction, as firewood and as fodder [8].

Fig. 1: *Ziziphus abyssinica* plant in its natural habitat

In Eritrea, it is used for charcoal, medicine, bees forage and as live fence [9] The result of phytochemical evaluation of the leaves of *Ziziphus abyssinica* shows the presence of fat and oil [10]. The herbalists in the northern community in Nigeria utilise the decoction of the root in the treatment of many ailments including mental disorders, diarrhea and abdominal ulcer [7].

Previous studies on this plant revealed its antibacterial and antioxidant properties [11]. The phytochemical, acute toxicity and antiulcer properties of this plant have also been evaluated [12].

Thus, this study aimed to produce biodiesel from *Ziziphus abyssinica* using magnetic sand as a heterogeneous catalyst, as a substitute to petroleum diesel.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection and Preparation

Dry and mature *Ziziphus abyssinica* fruits were collected from Ngamboru market Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. *Ziziphus abyssinica* seed (3kg) was used, the seeds were then removed. The seeds oil was roasted at temperature of 100°C for about 30 minutes and ground to tiny coarse particle sizes which were sieved using a sieve prior to oil extraction. Oil was extracted from the seeds using soxhlet extraction method. On a dry matter basis, the percentage yield was calculated.

Transesterification Procedure

The method described by Taufiq-Yap et al. [13] and Veljkovic et al. [14] were adopted for the production of biodiesel from non-edible vegetable oil of *Ziziphus abyssinica* seed. The uniqueness of this investigation was the heterogeneous system that was created to investigate the production of biodiesel. It involved the use of heterogeneous base catalysts Fe₃O₄, MgO and Fe₃O₄/MgO. Biodiesel production was carried out in at two-neck round-bottom flask reactor equipped with a reflux condenser stirrer. The reaction flask was immersed in a glass chamber placed on the plate of a magnetic stirrer (800rpm).

The temperature was varied between 45°C and 65°C by water circulating from a thermostat by means of a pump. Typically, MgO Fe₃O₄ and Mg/O/Fe₃O₄ (1-5wt %) were suspended in a required volume of methanol. Subsequently, oil was varied into the mixture under continuous stirring.

The methanol/oil molar ratio was varied between 3:1-5:1 at the end of reaction (1-5hrs), the catalyst was separated via centrifugation and the reaction mixture was then loaded into a rotary evaporator to remove excess methanol. Experiment was carried out by varying different parameters like methanol/oil molar ratio, reaction time and catalyst amount. Conversion of *Ziziphus abyssinica* seed oil to biodiesel by MgO, Fe₃O₄ and MgO/Fe₃O₄ was compared. Since the transesterification of triglycerides can produce methyl ester (biodiesel) and by product glycerol, the conversion of oil was calculated based on the amount of recovered methyl ester (biodiesel).

Oil Characterization

Determination of Free Fatty Acid (FFA)

Determination of free fatty acid is based on AOAC method [11]. About 0.5 g of sample oil was boiled with 5 mL of ethanol and was allowed to cool. About 2 drops of phenolphthalein indicator were added and titrated with 0.1M NaOH until pink colour disappears, free fatty acid was calculated using the expression below.

$$\text{FFA} = \frac{V \times N_a \times F}{W_s} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where, V= Titre value, Na= Normality of acid. F= equivalent weight of free fatty acid, Ws = Weight of sample

Determination Acid Value

Determination of Acid Value was done according to AOAC method [15]. The acid value of the sample oil was determined by dissolving about 5.0-5.5g of the sample oil in a hot mixture of 25 ml diethyl ether and 25 mL 95% v/v ethyl alcohol.

The hot solution was neutralized with 0.1 M NaOH using phenolphthalein as indicator. The acid value was then determined using the equation below.

$$Av = \frac{M \times C \times T}{W} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Where M = Molar mass of KOH (56.1), C = Concentration of KOH (0.1 M).

Tv = Titre value, W = Weight of oil sample

Determination of Viscosity

The viscosity was determined by the Cannon-Fenske viscometer and a circulatory bath with temperature control. Viscosity was calculated using ASTM method D445-97[16]. The viscometer was washed and dried. The sample was sucked into it and was immersed into a circulatory bath set at 30°C. The time of flow of sample from upper mark to lower mark of the viscometer was recorded using a stop watch. The experiment was repeated thrice and the average flow time was recorded. This was carried out on oil before and after trans-esterification. The instrumental constant was obtained from the viscometer Thus viscosity of the sample was calculated using the formula below:

$$\text{Viscosity (V)} = KT \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where K = Instrumental constant. T= Efflux time (s)

Specific Gravity Determination

Specific gravity was determined according to the standard method contained in ASTM D5002 [17]. The sample oil was poured into a vertical glass cylinder and a hydrometer was placed in the oil and allowed to be stable, the value of the specific gravity was taken from the marking on the stem of the hydrometer at the surface of the oil.

Determination of Moisture Content

The ground seed (2g) was placed in a dried and weighed crucible. The crucible with the ground seed was placed in the Griffin temperature adjustable oven at 110°C. Heating and weighing was carried out at intervals of 1 (one) hour until a constant weight is obtained. The crucible was allowed to cool, the weight and percentage (%) moisture content was calculated [18].

Biodiesel Characterization

The physical and chemical properties of the biodiesel were investigated. Unlike the use of vegetable oils in the food industries, the petroleum industry has its own testing protocol for product evaluation [19]. The parameters assessed include: viscosities, density, acid value. Hash and pour point, moisture and ash content. Density and viscosity were measured using ASTM standards D129S and D445 respectively. Pour and flash points was determined using the ASTM methods D5773 and D 93 respectively.

Characterization of Catalysts

Analysis of catalysts using X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) characterization of the MgO, magnetic sand and MgO-magnetic sand catalysts were performed on a Empyrean (Panalytical model) based generator X-ray diffractometer. The analysed material was finely ground to pass through 63 microns, homogenized and average hulk composition was determined.

The powdered sample was then be prepared using the sample preparation block and compressed in the flat sample holder to create a flat, smooth surface that was later be mounted on the sample stage in the XRD cabinate. The sample was analysed using the reflection-transmission spinner stage using the Theta- Theta settings. About 20 stalling position was 0.00483 and ends at 75.000 with a 20 step of 0.026 at 3.57 seconds per step. Tube current was 40 mA and the tension was 45VA. Fixed Divergent Slit size of 1° was used and the goinometer radius was 240 mm. particle size was evaluated by means of Scherrer's equation [13].

The catalytic activities of the various solid catalyst samples were determined by using *Ziziphus abyssinica* seed oil conversion reaction to methyl esters at different temperatures varying between 45 and 65°C.

Crystal Size Determination

A Fityk 0.9.8 version software was used to obtain the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the XRD peaks. The crystallite size was obtained using a modified Scherrer equation.

Analysis of Bulk Chemical Composition of Magnetic Sand using X-ray Fluorescence (XRF)

X-ray fluorescence is an important analytical technique which is generally utilized in the determination of chemical composition of a given sample. Magnetic sand sample was prepared by reducing the particle size to less than 63 microns using a Tema vibrating mill. The agate motor in the mill crushes the sample before sieving it to pass through 63 microns. Beads used for the major elemental analysis expressed in oxide weight percent was prepared by first drying the sample powder in an oven at 110°C for 24hrs to remove the moisture in the sample. About 5.0 g of dry sample powder was weighed in the silica crucible and then ignited in the furnace at 1000 °C for 2 to 3h for the calcinations of impurities in the sample.

The sample was then be removed from the furnace and allowed to cool to room temperature in a desiccators. The ignited sample powder was then be weighed again to determine the weight of the calcinated impurities which are H₂O and CO₂. About 1.0 g of the stored ignited sample powder was weighed and exactly 5 times of flux [X-ray Flux-Type 66:34% (66.0% Lithium Tetraborate: 34% Lithium metaborate)] was added to lower the verification temperature of the sample powder.

The weighed mixture was mixed properly in a platinum dish and ignited in the pre-set furnace (Eggon 2 Automatic fuse bead maker) at 1500 °C for 10 minutes to form glass bead. The glass bead was then slotted into the computerized XRI- (Epsilon 5 Panalytical model) for major elemental analysis. Trace elemental analysis was carried out using compressed powder pellets. These pellets were prepared by weighing 3.0 g of oven dried powdered sample and 3.0g flux (cellulosic- powder) added as a binder and dispersive agent, and shaking in small plastic containers for 12 minutes. The well mixed mixture was then be compressed by applying pressure of 1500 Kg/m² using both manual and electronic compressors. The pellets were placed in the computer- programmed XRI' and the conditions for trace elemental set to give the result in elemental.

Ziziphus abyssinica a Seed Oil and its Methyl Ester Characterization using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometric (FT-IR) Technique

FT-IR is an effective analytical instrument for detecting functional groups and characterizing covalent bonding information. FT-IR spectrum of the biodiesel was obtained between 4000 and 400cm⁻¹ on a KBr powder using FT-IR spectrometer (Nicolet AVATAR 360).

RESULTS

Physicochemical Analysis

The physicochemical analysis of the *Ziziphus abyssinica* seed oil revealed that ash content 004%, specific gravity 0.98, moisture content 0.07%, acid value, 4.38 mg KOH/g , free fatty acid, 2.19% viscosity, 4.93 cSt and pH value 6.86, were presented in Table 1.

Biodiesel Quality

Table 2 presents the biodiesel quality parameters of physical characteristic in relation to known standard. The result shows that the pour point 3°C, 4°C and 6°C cloud point 8°C, 7°C and 6°C. flash point 183°C, 208°C and 241°C viscosity 5.4 cSt, 5.6 cSt and 5.3 cSt and pH value 8.9,8.7 and 8.9.

Energy Dispersive X-ray

The energy dispersive X-ray of magnetic sand revealed that silicon and potassium have the higher atomic and weight concentration while iron and titanium showed no concentration as presented in Table 3 The characterization results revealed high atomic concentration of Si (77.14%), followed by K (10.92%), Al (4.77%), Ca (1.50%), Fe (1.36%), S (1.11%), Ag (1.06%), P (0.66%), Mg (0.62%), Zr (0.60%) and Na (0.27%).

Energy dispersive X-ray of catalyst sample (MgO) obtained (Table 4) shows that magnesium has the higher atomic and weight concentration of 40.92 and 40.59, while titanium has the least value as shown in Table 4.4. Results revealed high atomic concentration of Mg (40.92 %), followed by C (36.74%), Zn (2.21%), Ca (1.89%), O (1.87%), S (1.84%), N (1.75%), K (1.68%), Si (1.66%), P (1.65%) Cl (1.58%), I (1.52%), Ag (1.50%), and Na (0.67%).

Energy dispersive X-ray of mixed magnetic Sand and MgO are presented in Table 5. The characterization results revealed high atomic concentration of Mg (48.71 %), followed by C (28.13%), Ca (3.21%), I (2.98%), Zn (2.21%), Ag (2.16%), K (2.01%), O (1.98%), N (1.94%), P (1.89%) Cl (1.84%), S (1.74%), Al (1.61%), Si (1.34%) and Na (0.45%). Magnesium has the higher atomic and weight concentration of 48.71 and 44.33, while Zn and Fe were not detected.

Table 1: Physicochemical analysis of the *Ziziphus abyssinica* seed oil

Property	Value
Ash content	0.04%
Specific gravity	0.98
Moisture content	0.07 %
Acid value	4.38 mg KOH/g
Free fatty acid	2.19 %
Viscosity	4.93 cSt
pH value	6.86

Table 2: Biodiesel Quality Parameters

Fuel Property	MOCZAME	MSCZAME	MOMSCZAME	(ASTMD6751) Limit	Specification US	Specification UK
Viscosity	5.4	5.6	5.3	1.9–6.0	1.9-6.0	3.5-5.0
Flash point (°C)	183	208	241	130	315-350	360
Cloud point (°C)	8	7	10	-3 – 12	-3-12	-
Pour point (°C)	3	4	6	-3 – 16	-15-10	-
pH value	8.9	8.7	8.9	-----	9	9

KEY: MOCZAME=Magnesium oxide catalyzed *Ziziphus abyssinica* methyl ester, MSCZAM=Magnetic sand catalyzed *Ziziphus abyssinica* methyl ester and MOMSCZAME=MgO/Magnetic sand catalysed *Ziziphus abyssinica* methyl ester

Table 3: Energy Dispersive X-ray of Magnetic Sand

Element Name	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.
Silicon	77.14	69.78
Potassium	10.92	13.76
Aluminium	4.77	4.14
Silver	1.06	3.69
Iron	1.36	2.45
Calcium	1.50	1.93
Zirconium	0.60	1.77
Sulfur	1.11	1.14
Phosphorus	0.66	0.66
Magnesium	0.62	0.48
Sodium	0.27	0.20
Titanium	0.00	0.00

Table 4: Energy dispersive X-ray of MgO

Element Name	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.
Magnesium	40.92	40.59
Carbon	36.74	18.01
Iodine	1.52	7.88
Silver	1.50	6.60
Zinc	2.21	5.89
Calcium	1.89	3.10
Potassium	1.68	2.69
Sulfur	1.84	2.41
Chlorine	1.58	2.29
Titanium	1.10	2.15
Phosphorus	1.65	2.09
Silicon	1.66	1.90
Aluminium	1.40	1.55
Oxygen	1.87	1.22
Nitrogen	1.75	1.00
Sodium	0.67	0.63
Iron	0.00	0.00

Table 5: Energy dispersive X-ray of mixed magnetic sand and MgO

Element Name	Atomic Conc.	Weight Conc.
Magnesium	48.71	44.33
Iodine	2.98	14.16
Carbon	28.13	12.65
Silver	2.16	8.74
Calcium	3.21	4.81
Potassium	2.01	2.95
Chlorine	1.84	2.44
Phosphorus	1.89	2.19
Sulfur	1.74	2.09
Aluminium	1.61	1.62
Silicon	1.34	1.41
Oxygen	1.98	1.19
Nitrogen	1.94	1.02
Sodium	0.45	0.39
Zinc	0.00	0.00
Iron	0.00	0.00

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectral Study

The result of the FTIR spectra of the *Ziziphus abyssinica* seed oil, magnesium oxide *Ziziphus abyssinica* methyl ester, magnetic sand catalyzed *Ziziphus abyssinica* Methyl ester and MgO/Magnetic sand catalyzed *Ziziphus abyssinica* methyl ester presented in Figure 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively

Figure 6 shows the XRD spectrum of magnetic sand pattern from 0° - 70°, 2 θ angle reveals the nature of the sand to have peaks at around 19.4°, 21.5°, 25°, 27°, 28°, 28.8° 37°, 40°, 40.7°, 50.7°, 55.3° 60.3, 65° and 69° are presented.

XRD Spectral Analysis

Figure 7 the XRD spectrum of MgO have the main peaks 2 θ = 28° that the powder is crystalline and their crystalline was shown at 2 θ = 29.3°, 34.5°, 38°, 43°, 51°, 59° and 62° their diffraction peaks was shown at 2 θ = 38° was presented.

Figure 8 shows the main peaks as follows, 19.4°, 21.5°, 25°, 27°, 28°, 28.8° 37°, 40°, 40.7°, 50.7°, 55.3° 60.3, 65° and 69° were all present in the XRD spectrum of Sand/MgO but their intensities ha significantly increased. So also, their broadness ware all presented.

Figure 9 show the image of sand, SEM analysis. The size of the crystal line was measured to be 100 μ m with uniform XRD.

Figure 10 presents the image of MgO sample SEM analysis of MgO was highly agglomerated and porous in nature with uniform size distribution. Sample formed a group of non-uniform crystalline particles.

Figure 11 shows the sand and magnesium structure, sand-MgO. It has been observed that the mixture of the two samples caused a substantial decrease in particle size, which may obviously account for the combined nature of the crystalline.

The variation of methanol to oil mole ratio on methyl yield, is shown in Figure 12. It revealed the influence of MgO, magnetic sand and MgO/magnetic sand catalysts on the conversion of triglycerides to methyl-esters. The catalysts amount was varied in the range of 1.0wt% and 5.0wt% oil is presented in Figure 12.

Variation of reaction temperature on methyl ester yield temperature has a profound effect on the rate at which chemical reactions occur. In Figure 13 was presented.

Figure 14 shows the conversion of *Ziziphus abyssinica* oil versus reaction time. The result revealed that, the slowness of the reaction within short reaction time can be attributed to the presence of heterogeneous mass transfer systems as presented in Figure 14.

Figure 15 shows the variation of amount of catalyst [w%] on methyl ester yield. The most notable catalyst used in producing biodiesel is the homogeneous alkaline catalysts this is due to their higher kinetic reaction rates was presented in Figure 15.

Fig. 2: FT-IR spectrum of the *Z. abyssinica* seed oil

Fig. 4: FT-IR spectrum of magnetic sand catalyzed *Z. abyssinica* methyl ester

Fig. 3: FTIR spectrum of magnesium oxide catalyzed *Z. abyssinica* methylester

Fig. 5: FT-IR spectrum of MgO/Magnetic sand catalysed *Z. abyssinica* methyl ester

Fig. 6: XRD spectrum of the magnetic sand

Fig. 7: XRD spectrum of MgO

Fig. 8: XRD spectrum of mixed magnetic sand and MgO

Figure 9: SEM of magnetic sand

Figure 10: SEM of MgO

Figure 11: SEM of mixed magnetic sand and MgO

Fig. 12: SEM of mixed magnetic sand and MgO

Fig. 13: Variation of methanol to oil molar ratio on methyl ester yield

Fig. 14: Variation of reaction temperature on methyl ester yield

Fig. 15: Variation of reaction time on methyl ester yield

DISCUSSION

The ash content of the oil (Table 1) is 0.04%. This value is considered reasonable. The specific gravity was found to be 0.98%. The moisture content was determined to be 0.07%. Moisture content is the amount of water contained in the oil sample [20]. Higher moisture content in oils leads to enzymatic reactions which affect other properties of the oil such as acid value, free Fatty acid and peroxide value [21]. The measure of the free fatty acid content in oil can be indicated by its acid value. Acid value is an indicator of the edibility of oil and its suitability for industrial use [22]. The acid value of the oil was determined to be 4.38% which is so much higher than that reported by Babakura *et al.* [23] (0.140%); Danbature *et al.* [24] and Yelwa *et al.* [25] (0.15mgKOH/g). The low acid value demonstrates the feasibility of alkali – catalyzed transesterification (Danbature *et al.* [24]). Free fatty acids are produced by the hydrolysis of oils and fats. Fatty acids are carboxylic acids with a long aliphatic which may be either saturated or unsaturated [25]. The free fatty acid of this oil was determined to be 2.19%. Viscosity is a resistant to flow exhibited by the oil [25]. The viscosity of the oil obtained to be 4.93 cSt which is within the standard of ASTM D6751 value of 1.9-6.0. The obtained specific gravity (0.98) competes favorably with those of Canola oil (0.9;0.92g/ml) and soybean (0.92;0.89g/ml) as reported by Abayeh *et al.* [21]. The obtained specific gravity and density are important physical characteristics indicative of the handling and storage of oils and fuels [18].

Table 2 shows the physical characteristic of the biodiesels in relation to known standard. From the table, it can be seen that the pour point, cloud point, flash point, density and the viscosity of the biodiesel were found to be within ASTM D6751 standard for biodiesel specification. A similar trend was obtained from the biodiesel produced from *Khaya senegalensis* seed oil by Babakura *et al.* [23]. Conversely, the viscosity and pour are higher than that reported by Danbature *et al.* [24] while cloud point, and flash point are lower than those reported by same Danbature *et al.* [24]. Although, the flash point of the oil falls within the standards but it is lower than those of sunflower and rape seeds methyl esters (Reference?). Therefore, these biodiesels can ignite at a higher temperature than those of the other oils.

Pour point represents the lowest temperature at which oil is capable of flowing under gravity. It is one of the important low-temperature characteristics of high-boiling fractions. Biodiesel were found to be within ASTM D6751 standard for biodiesel specification. A similar trend was obtained from the biodiesel produced from *Khaya senegalensis* seed oil [23]. Conversely, the viscosity and pour are higher than that reported by Danbature *et al.* [24]. The use of *Ziziphus abyssinica* oil methyl esters in colder regions is limited. However, this value is also indicative of the high potential of this fuel as biodiesel particularly in Northern Nigeria where temperature is always above 20°C, a temperature at which the oil is fluid [23].

Ash content represents the inorganic residue (minerals) remaining after ignition and complete oxidation of organic matter. All the biodiesel sample produced from *Ziziphus abyssinica* oil had ash content of 0.04% and were lower compared to that of crude oil which was obtained as 0.07%. The ash content describes the number of inorganic contaminants such as abrasive solids and catalyst residues, and the concentration of soluble metal soaps contained in a fuel sample [24].

The flash point is a general indication of the flammability. Flash points are lower than those reported by same [24]. Although, the flash point of the oil falls within the standards but it is lower than those of sunflower and rape seeds methyl esters. Therefore, these biodiesels can ignite at a higher temperature than those of the other oils. One of the most important characteristics of any fuel is its flash point. Flash point is the temperature that indicates the overall flammability hazards in the presence of air; higher flash points make for safe handling and storage of biodiesel.

Density is an important biodiesel parameter, with impact on fuel quality. Predicting density is of high relevance for a correct formulation of an adequate blend of raw materials that optimize the cost of biodiesel fuel production while allowing the produced fuel to meet the required quality standards. The biodiesel was found to be within ASTM D6751 standard for biodiesel specification. A similar trend was obtained from the biodiesel produced from *Khaya senegalensis* seed oil by Babakura *et al.* [23]. The density of diesel oil is important because it gives an indication of the delay between the injection and combustion of the fuel in a diesel engine (ignition quality) and the energy per unit mass.

Viscosity is the degree of a material's resistance to flow, high viscous materials flow with great difficulty, while less viscous ones flow with ease. Linus *et al.* [26]. It causes the formation of engine deposits as it affects the atomization of a fuel upon injection into the combustion chamber, the higher the viscosity, the greater the propensity of the fuel to cause such problems. The kinematic viscosity value of the biodiesel decreases with increase in temperature [27]. The viscosity of the biodiesel was found to be within ASTM D6751 standard for biodiesel specification, a gradual decrease in viscosity was observed in the crude luffa oil and its methylesters with temperature. The result agrees with theoretical claims which opine that viscosity decreases with an increase in temperature.

Electron Dispersive X-ray (EDX) is a useful technique to probe both the elemental composition of the surface of catalysts and the oxidation state and electronic environment of each component EDX data revealed the compositions of the synthesized materials from the sand, MgO and Sand/MgO. Table 3 present the compositional values obtained from the EDX analysis of the prepared sand. The characterization results revealed high atomic concentration of Si (77.14 %), followed by K (10.92%), Al (4.77%), Ca (1.50%), Fe (1.36%), S (1.11%), Ag (1.06%), P (0.66%), Mg (0.62%), Zr (0.60%) and Na (0.27%). This result is in different ratio has effect on chemical and physical properties. Recent investigation [15] shows that all types of soils have more or less complex mineralogical composition.

A Typical EDX recorded in MgO powder is shown in Table 4. As can be seen, the powder is composed of O and Mg. The characterization results revealed high atomic concentration of Mg (40.92 %), followed by C (36.74%), Zn (2.21%), Ca (1.89%), O (1.87%), S (1.84%), N (1.75%), K (1.68%), Si (1.66%), P (1.65%) Cl (1.58%), I (1.52%), Ag (1.50%), and Na (0.67%).

The characterization results revealed high atomic concentration of Mg (48.71 %), followed by C (28.13%), Ca (3.21%), I (2.98%), Zn (2.21%), Ag (2.16%), K (2.01%), O (1.98%), N (1.94%), P (1.89%) Cl (1.84%), S (1.74%), Al (1.61%), Si (1.34%) and Na (0.45%).

The quantitative results of Mg thin films from Table 4.5 indicated that the atomic concentration for Mg increases from 40.92 % to 48.71% this may be due to the Mg present in the Sand that happened to found itself as a result of mixing Sand with MgO. This also shows that the mixing ratio can be controlled. It can be seen that with increasing the size of the particle and the amount of Mg, the amount of C decreases from 36.74 to 28.13%. The amount of Zinc from the EDX of MgO was 2.21% which reduced to 0.00% in EDX of sand/MgO. The amounts of Ca increased from 1.89% to 3.21%, Ag increased from 1.50% in MgO to 2.16%, K increased from 1.68% in MgO to 2.01% in Sand/MgO. Oxygen increased from 1.87% to 1.98%, Nitrogen increased from 1.75% to 1.94%, Phosphorus from 1.68% to 1.89%, Cl increased from 1.68% to 1.84%, Al increased from 1.40% to 1.61%, However, Sulfur decreased from 1.84% to 1.74%, Silicon decreased from 1.66% down to 1.34% and Na 0.67% down to 0.45%. The results of the EDX analysis confirm that the deposited films are very close to the nominal composition.

FT-IR spectrometry is a rapid and precise method for identifies the main functional groups presence at both the optimally produced biodiesel sample and its parent waste vegetable oil [25]. The most characteristic absorption peaks of the vegetable oil were indicated in Figure 2. The sharp peaks observed at 2862.46 cm^{-1} and 2916.47 cm^{-1} are characteristic of C-H stretches associated with the methane hydrogen atoms. The band at 1743.971 cm^{-1} was assigned to the C = O stretching of saturated ester [25]. The band at 1450.52 cm^{-1} corresponds to the characteristics of C-H of

alkane bending vibration and the band at 1149.61 cm^{-1} was attributed to the C-O bond stretching [25]. The absorption peak appearing at 717.54 cm^{-1} is representative of $-\text{CH}_2$.

Figure 3 showed the IR spectra of magnesium oxide catalyzed *Ziziphus abyssinica* methyl ester in this spectrum a dominant band at 3309.96 cm^{-1} is due to the O-H stretching vibration, antisymmetric stretching vibration at 2955.04 cm^{-1} and 2823.88 cm^{-1} were also due to $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{CH}_2$ which is similar to one detected by [25]. The C=O stretching vibration associated with acetate groups with a molecular vibration at 1743.71 cm^{-1} was detected and complemented by one intense peaks at 1454.61 cm^{-1} due to the $-\text{CH}_3$ bending vibration [25]. The peaks appearing at 1427.37 cm^{-1} which is the methyl ($-\text{CH}_3$) ester group ($\text{COO}-\text{CH}_3$) and another intense peak was detected at 1026.16 cm^{-1} which correspond to the asymmetric stretching mode of $-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}-$ of ester groups [25].

Figure 4 showed a peak at 3325.39 cm^{-1} which is due to the presence of O-H stretching vibration, intense peaks at 2962.76 cm^{-1} and 2823.88 cm^{-1} correspond to the $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{CH}_2$ anti-symmetric stretching vibration similar to the one obtained by Yelwa et al., 2017. A molecular vibration at 1790 cm^{-1} is an indicative of C=O stretching vibration. Intense peaks at 1454.61 cm^{-1} due to the $-\text{CH}_3$ bending vibration [25]. The peaks appearing at 1419.66 cm^{-1} which is the methyl ester group ($\text{CO}-\text{O}-\text{CH}_3$) and another intense peak was detected at 1018.45 cm^{-1} according to the asymmetric stretching mode of $-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}-$ of ester groups [25].

Figure 5 showed a dominant band at 3309.96 cm^{-1} that is due to the O-H stretching vibration, different intense peaks at such as the doublet of the $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{CH}_2$ anti-symmetric stretching vibration at 2962.76 cm^{-1} and 2823.88 cm^{-1} were also detected [25]. C=O stretching vibration associated with acetate groups with a molecular vibration at 1705.13 cm^{-1} was detected and complemented by one intense peaks at 1419.66 cm^{-1} due to the $-\text{CH}_3$ bending vibration [25]. The peaks appearing at 1419.66 cm^{-1} which is the methyl ester group ($\text{CO}-\text{O}-\text{CH}_3$) and another intense peaks was detected at 1026.16 cm^{-1} according to the asymmetric stretching mode of $-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}-$ of ester groups [25]. Figure 6, 7 and 8 depict the XRD patterns of the magnesium oxide, magnetic sand and magnesium oxide and magnetic sand (sand, MgO and sand/MgO). The XRD results are represented as A, B, and C. The XRD patterns from $0^\circ - 70^\circ$, 2θ angle revealed the nature of the sand to have peaks at around 19.4° , 21.5° , 25° , 27° , 28° , 28.8° , 37° , 40° , 40.7° , 50.7° , 55.3° , 60.3° , 65° and 69° and the main peak at $2\theta = 28^\circ$.

The XRD spectrum of MgO powder at room temperature. From the peak width, it can be inferred that the powder is crystalline. The X-ray diffraction pattern of MgO consist of the main diffraction peaks at around $2\theta = 29.3^\circ$, 34.5° , 38° , 43° , 51° , 59° and 62°), and the main peak at $2\theta = 38^\circ$, this result is in agreement with the standard XRD of MgO reported by Edeh *et al.* [28]. The XRD patterns of sand/MgO catalyst. From the XRD spectrum of the sand sample it was observed that the peaks at around 19.4° , 21.5° , 25° , 27° , 28° , 28.8° , 37° , 40° , 40.7° , 50.7° , 55.3° , 60.3° , 65° and 69° were all present in the XRD spectrum of Sand/MgO but their intensities has significantly increased; So also, their broadness.

The SEM image of magnesium oxide, magnetic sand and magnesium oxide and magnetic sand (sand, MgO and sand/MgO) particles are shown in Fig. 9, 10 and 11. SEM analysis was remarkable method for showing the surface morphologies of solid materials. The sample A, B and C observed to have a definite morphology with a crystal structure (aligning with XRD pattern obtained), and the size of the crystalline was measured to be $100\mu\text{m}$ with a uniform distribution. It can be observed that there was a good dispersion from all the images from the samples. A closely and neatly packed spherical granule was found in the sand (A). It is observed that the (B) MgO were highly agglomerated and porous in nature with uniform size distribution. Sample B and C formed a group of non-uniform crystalline particles. C) Shows the sand and magnesium structure change from MgO to sand-MgO. It has been observed that the mixture of the two samples caused a substantial decrease in particle size, which may obviously account for the combined nature of the crystalline.

The conversion of *Ziziphus abyssinica* oil in the presence of the catalysts exhibited a strong dependence on the methanol to oil ratio. When the methanol loading amount was increased, the conversion was increased considerably. The maximum conversion of all three catalysts was obtained at a molar ratio of 15:1. As shown in Figure 12 which is catalyzed by heterogeneous catalysts. The most notable catalyst used in producing biodiesel is the homogeneous alkaline catalyst. The choice of catalysts is due to their higher kinetic reaction rates. However, because of high cost of refined feedstocks and difficulties associated with use of homogeneous alkaline catalysts to trans esterify low quality feedstocks for biodiesel production, development of various heterogeneous catalysts is now on the increase [29].

Temperature has a profound effect on the rate at which chemical reactions occur. Figure 13 shows how *Ziziphus abyssinica* methylester yield increased with increase in temperature. The MgO/ magnetic sand catalyst gave the highest yield followed by MgO and lastly magnetic sand at 65°C. higher reaction temperature increases the reaction rate and shortened the reaction time due to the reduction in viscosity of oils [30]. Insufficient amount of catalyst leads to the incomplete conversion of triglycerides into fatty acid esters [30].

Figure 14 shows the conversion of *Ziziphus abyssinica* oil versus reaction time. The slowness of the reaction within short reaction time can be attributed to the presence of heterogeneous mass transfer systems [13]. The conversion was low at first 3 hours. However, it can be seen that the conversion for these three catalysts were increased gradually after 4hours of reaction time. The MgO/ magnetic sand catalyst showed the highest conversion in shorter time as compared to MgO and magnetic sand. Heterogeneous catalysts are environmentally friendly, economical and have high chance for heat integration [31]. longer reaction time leads to the reduction of end product (biodiesel) due to the reversible reaction of transesterification resulting in loss of esters as well as soap formation [32].

Figure 15 showed the biodiesel production is widely conducted through transesterification reaction, soap formation (saponification) leads to the loss of catalyst and decreasing yields in the reaction products, and the greater the amount of soap formation, the greater the consumption of oil. The loss of catalyst also reduces its reuse potential. Soap formation was determined after the conversion of oil to biodiesel, the biodiesel conversion as a function of the catalyst concentration and reaction time [33]. When the concentration of catalyst is increased with oil samples, the conversion of triglycerides into biodiesel is also increased. Catalyst concentration above 5% the conversion starts within a short time and then stabilizes. The best results were obtained when 5% of catalyst concentration was used [33].

CONCLUSION

The finding of this study revealed that, the magnetic sand obtained at a random from Gadabull river was found to exhibit catalytic activity in the conversion of *Ziziphus abyssinica* seed oil to its methyl-ester as further proved by FT-IR analysis. A discovery such as this is indeed an addition to the indigenous catalysts that are cheap and easily accessible. The finding also shows that the pour point, cloud point, flash point, density and the viscosity of the biodiesel were found to be within ASTM D6751 standard for biodiesel specification hence the used of this plant in the production of biodiesel get scientific backing. Likewise, the temperature, amount of catalyst and reaction time has effect on the yield of biodiesel.

REFERENCES

1. Antony-Raja S, Robinson SDS, & Lindon RLC. Biodiesel Production from Jatropha oil and its Characterization. *Research Journal of Chemical Science*, 2011: 1(1), 81–87.
2. Van Der PE, Franken IV, & De Jongh J. General data on Jatropha, In: J. De Jong, ed., *The Jatropha handbook: from Cultivation to Application*, 1st ed., Eindhoven: FACT Foundation. 2010, pp. 1-7.
3. Demirbas A. Biodiesel from Sunflower Oil in Supercritical Methanol with Calcium Oxide. *Energy Conservation and Management*, 2007:48, 937-941.
4. Gui MM, Lee KT, & Bhatia S. Feasibility of Edible Oil vs. Non-Edible Oil vs. Waste Edible Oil as Biodiesel Feedstock. *Energy*, 2008:33(11), 1646 – 1653.
5. Mittelbach M, Schober S, & Spencer G. The influence of antioxidants on the oxidation stability of biodiesel. *Journal of American Chemical Society*, 2008:80, 1380-1384.
6. Kucek KT, Cesar Oliveira MAF, Wilhelm HM & Ramos LP. Ethanolysis of Refined Soybean Oil Assisted by Sodium and Potassium Hydroxides. *Journal of American Oil Chemists Society*, 2007:84(4), 385-392.
7. Bournay L, Casanave D, Delfort B, Hillion G, & Chodorge JA. New Heterogeneous Process for Biodiesel Production: A way to Improve the Quality and the Value of the Crude Glycerin Produced by Biodiesel Plants. *Catalysis Today*. 2005:106 (1-4), 190-192.
8. Ward D, Shrestha MK, & Musli I. (2006). Are invasive mistletoe killing *Ziziphus spina-christi*? *Isreal Journal of Plant Science*, 2006:54(2), 113-117.
9. Chikamai B, Eyog-Matig O, & Mbogga M. Review and Appraisal on the Status of Indigenous Fruits in Eastern Africa A report prepared for IPGRI-SAFORGEN in the Framework of AFREA/FORNESSA. 2004.
10. Ibrahim JA, Egharevba HO, Nnamdi RA, & Kunle, OF. Comparative pharmacognostic and phytochemical analysis of *Ziziphus spina-christi* (L.) Desf. and *Ziziphus abyssinica* Hochst. Ex A. Rich. *International Journal Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry Research*, 2015, 7(6): 1160-1166.
11. Canakci M. The Potential of Restaurant Waste Lipids as Biodiesel Feedstocks. *Bioresource Technology*, 2007:98(1), 183-190.

12. Cao F, Chen Y, Zhai F, Li J, Wang J, Wang X, Wang S, & Zhu W. Biodiesel Production from High Acid Value Waste Frying Oil Catalyzed by Superacid Heteropolyacid. *Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 2008:101(1), 93-100.
13. Taufiq-Yap YH, Lee HV, Haussein MZ, & Yunus R. Calcium base-catalyzed transesterification of *Jatropha curcas* oil to biodiesel. *Human and Bioenergy*. 2010:7(2), 1-22.
14. Veljkovic VB, Lakicevic SH, Stamenkovic OS, Todorovic ZB, & Lazic ML. Biodiesel production from tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum* L.) seed oil with a high content of free fatty acids. *Energ. Fuel*. 2006: **85**, 2671–2675.
15. AOAC: Association of official analytical chemists. Official Methods of Analysis, 14th edition Vol. 67 Association of official Analytical Chemist, Arlington. 1990.
16. ASTM (American society for testing and materials) (2008). Standard Specification for Biodiesel Fuel (B100) Blend Stock for Distillate Fuels. In: Annual Book of ASTM Standard, ASTM International, West Conshohocken method D6751-08.
17. ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials) (1998). Standard Specification for Biodiesel Fuel Oil. In: Annual Book of ASTM Standard, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, Method D975-089.
18. Abayeh OM, Garba HI, Adamu HM & Abayeh OJ. Quality Characteristics of *Luffa aegyptica* seed oil. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Research*, 2013:4(4), 11-16
19. Liston BJ. Biodegradation/Biodegradation/Biobased Lubricants and greases. *International Journal of Bioengineering*, 1993:5, 40-48.
20. Yelwa JM, Osemeahon SA, Nkafamiya II, & Abdullahi S. Synthesis and Characterization of Hydroxylated Sunflower Seed Oil/ Poly Vinyl Acetate Copolymers Binder for Possible Application in the Coating Industry, *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies*, 2017:4(1), 417-418.
21. Abayeh OM, Garba HI, Adamu HM & Abayeh OJ. Quality Characteristics of *Luffa aegyptica* Seed Oil. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Research*, 2013:4(4), 11-16.
22. AbuSayed M, Abbas AM, Sohel FI, Astaq M, Kahn G, & Sarmina YM. Physico-chemical Characteristics of *Mesua ferrea* Seed Oil and Nutritional Composition of its Seed and Leaves. *Bulletin of Chemical Society of Ethiopia*, 2004:18(2), 157-166.
23. Babakura M, Jibrin M Y, Abubakar I, Bashir MA, Jibrin YY, Jamilu BU, Musa MA, & Alexender OO. Synthesis and Characterization of Biodiesel from *Khaya senegalensis* Seed Oil using Heterogeneous Catalyst. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies*, 2019:29(4),101-106.
24. Danbature WL, Aliyu J, & Adamu HM. Production of Methyl Ester from Mahogany (*Khaya senegalensis*) Seed Oil. *Journal of Chemistry and Chemical Science*, 2015:5(9), 489-499.
25. Yelwa JM, Osemeahon SA, Nkafamiya II, & Abdullahi S. Synthesis and Characterization of Hydroxylated Sunflower Seed Oil/ Poly Vinyl Acetate Copolymers Binder for Possible Application in the Coating Industry, *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies*, 2017:4(1), 417-418.
26. Linus NO, Sedoo VB, Nwamaka RE, & Bello YM. Synthesis, Calorimetric and Viscometric Study of Groundnut oil Biodiesel and Blends. *Research Journal of Chemical Sciences*, 2011:1(3)
27. Knothe G. Viscosity of Biodiesel. Gerhard Knothe, Jon Van Gerpen and Jürgen Krahl, (Eds). The Biodiesel Handbook, 2nd Edition. 2005: Pp 89-90.
28. Edeh F, Joel, JM, Yelwa JM, & Barminas, JT. Development and Characterization of Heterogeneous Kaolin/Ash Based Catalyst System. *Material Science Indian Journal*, 2018:16(3), 23-38.
29. Atadashi IM, Aroua MK, Abdul Aziz AR, & Sulaiman NMN. The Effects of Catalysts in Biodiesel Production: A Review. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, 2013:19(1),14-26.
30. Leung DYC, & Guo Y. Transesterification of Neat and used Frying Oil: Optimization for Biodiesel Production. *Fuel Processing Technology*, 2006:87, 883-890.
31. Aransiola E, Betiku E, Layokun S, & Solomon B. Production of Biodiesel by Transesterification of Refined Soybean Oil. *International Journal of Biology and Chemical Science*, 2014:4(2), 391-399.
32. Eevera T, Rajendran K, & Saradha S. Biodiesel Production Process Optimization and Characterization to Assess the Suitability of the Product for Varied Environmental Conditions. *Renewable Energy*, 2009:34, 762– 765.
33. Evandro LD, Paulo T, Pedro T, & Carlos AK. Use of Heterogeneous Catalysts in Methylic Biodiesel Production Induced by Microwave Irradiation. *Química Nova*, 2014:37(3), 10-23.